

Managing Editor's Column

Vol. 8, No. 11; November 28, 2002

Dear Readers:

This is the last but one issue of a successful J.UCS year. Thus, it is time to remind our readers to renew their subscriptions (http://www.jucs.org/jucs_subscription.html), our authors to think about submitting a good paper and our editors to consider editing a special issue!

Also, although several university libraries have already purchased the archive editions of J.UCS, copies are still available. To remind you: the printed editions of J.UCS from the years 1997 - 2001 can be ordered by faxing us the order form from http://www.jucs.org/jucs_subscription/print.html. Furthermore, a number of recently published special issues such as the topical issue on Knowledge Management are also available in printed form and can be ordered from http://www.jucs.org/jucs_subscription/print.html as well.

Whether subscriber, author or editor - I look forward to hearing from you soon and thank you for your continuous support of J.UCS!

Cordially,

A handwritten signature in black ink, appearing to read 'H. Maurer', with a long horizontal flourish extending to the right.

Hermann Maurer
email: hmaurer@iicm.edu